

Design and Implementation New Techniques to Prevent Trojan Thread in Parallel CORDIC

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Abstract—Trojan thread affects the Integrated Circuit (IC) and changes its operation. Trojan thread is injected to the designs that have no security or weak security. After inserting Trojan thread, the IC operates in different behavior other than the intended behavior. The aim of the Trojan thread is to defect the IC operation or leak information from the IC to another IC through established link wired or wireless to the attacker. The presence of Trojan thread in IC lead to high losses and increase the defective products. There for it is very important to decrease the effect of the Trojan thread. In this paper we insert Trojan thread inside Coordinate Rotation Digital Computer (CORDIC) and see its effect and represent techniques to increase the design immunity against the Trojan thread.

Keywords— Trojan Thread, Voting Algorithm, Lockup Table Technique.

I. INTRODUCTION

The IC security is very important nowadays due to the spread of the Computer devices in our life applications. Without security we will be under the mercy of attackers. The IC with design weakness in security or implemented with hardware defects is subjected to hardware attacks. Nowadays, multiple companies are collaborating in designing and manufacturing the IC, so this collaboration with no security embedded in the IC will make the IC subjected to the hardware attacks. The security issue appears clearly in the Internet of Things (IoT) chips due to the cost and power restrictions. This power and cost limitations will decrease the security level. Cisco expect that the number of IoT ICs connected to the internet by 2020 will be 50 billion ICs [1]. The less power and low-cost IC are the targets for all the IoT companies. These limitations in power and cost prevent us from using software security stack to run on weak processor in the IC. The old ICs that already manufactured in the beginning of IoT revolution miss the concept of security in its design. These old ICs can be the open door to the attackers to attack out IC remotely.

The IC consists of multiple intellectual property (IP) connected together. These IPs are delivered from third party companies. These third party companies may depend on outsourced engineers for design or testing. Tools from different companies are used also in designing or manufacturing. The Trojan thread maybe inserted in the Register transfer level (RTL) of the IP, also the simulation tool or manufacturing tool can insert the Trojan thread, or the testing engineers can inject Trojan thread inside the IC [2], [3].

If the IC didn't perform its task as described in the design documents after fabrication then we are under hardware

attack. This hardware attack can be simple that occur every time with the same pattern, or it can be randomly appeared. This randomly appearance will make the debugging more difficult. The activation of hardware attack can depend on internal pattern appearance or from external input. The internal pattern like observing certain sequence of input data or defecting range of input data. The external trigger can come through pad input from another IC. This Trojan thread need to be isolated during the design of the chip. In the next section we will discuss the different techniques to isolate or detract effect of the Trojan thread.

II. HARDWARE ATTACKS ELIMINATION

A. Dynamic Permutation

This solution changes the order of the data from the input and feed permuted data to the core as shown in figure 1. If the Trojan thread use certain pattern to start the attack, this permutation will change this pattern. This will give the core immunity against the hardware attack. The permutation core can choose from different permutation patterns. These patterns will make it harder for the Trojan thread to attack the core. We can use random number generator to control this dynamic permutation patterns. If the permutation core detects hardware failure then it will request new permutation pattern with random number generated. This method will make the data encrypted inside the IC, and make the IC immune against the hardware attacks [4].

Fig. 1. Dynamic permutation technique.

B. Network on Chip

The network on chip (NoC) is network-based architecture. NoC connect modules together on the IC. We Can use the concept of the NoC to remove the effect of the trojan thread. NOC is based on routers that is implemented in the IC, so we can treat NoC as network between the modules in the IC connected together through routers. The function of the router is to understand the data packet header information, then forwarding this packet to the next routing router. If there is

change in the module due to hardware attack, then the header of the packet will be affected from this hardware attack. The router will see errors in packet header come from infected module. At this case, the router will stop the data packet come from the infected module and isolate it, so this infected module will not affect rest of the IC [5].

C. Voting Algorithm

This technique depends on adding multiple cores which make the same task on the integrated circuit. These cores are implemented in different companies. This design technique will decrease the effect of hardware attack on the IC. These different cores are connected to controller which choose the agreed outputs from the three cores and connect it to the global outputs. If there is attack happen on one of these cores then the controller will see difference between the outputs and will make voting between different outputs and choose the majority outputs from the cores' outputs, then connect it to the global outputs.

D. Lockup Table

The lockup table contains few expected outputs from model of the core, or from design calculations. The controller will be connected to two cores with the same function from different companies. The controller will compare the outputs from two cores according to the expected values in the lockup table. If there is difference between the values in the lockup table and the outputs from any of the cores then the controller will ignore all the outputs from the infected core and connect the main outputs to the Core which its outputs match the lockup table values.

III. TROJAN THREAD ATTACK

We will use the Rotation Digital Computer (CORDIC) as an example of module that will be affected by Trojan thread. The CORDIC is used to calculate the trigonometric functions for the input angle [6], [7]. The Trojan thread inserted will affect certain range of input angles. This range in our hardware attack design is from 45° to 60°. If the input angle

locates in the attacked range then the Trojan thread will affect the CORDIC outputs by applying zeros to the outputs. The Trojan controller randomize number which will calculate the appearances of blocked input angles. These number will make the Trojan thread wait before starting attack. This randomization will make the debugging more complex.

The Trojan thread architecture as shown in figure 2 is simple counter that counts the number of appearances of blocked input angles, this counter is followed by controller which compare the count with the random count feed from random generator. If the counter value equals the random count, then it will activate multiplexer which will connect the outputs to zeros.

Figure 3 shows the outputs of CORDIC after inserting the Trojan thread inside it, when there is input angle in the range of blocked angles, the CORDIC outputs become zeros.

Fig. 2. Trojan thread architecture.

Fig. 3. Trojan thread affects CORDIC output.

IV. TROJAN THREAD EXCLUSION

A. Voting Algorithm

Using the voting technique, we will make simulation using three different CORDIC cores, the first and the third cores are normal cores without any hardware attacks. The second core will suffer from Trojan thread inserted in it. The outputs of the infected CORDIC will be zeros if the input angle in the range of blocked angles [45° to 60°]. The voting controller will compare between the three outputs and if there is one CORDIC core outputs different to the other two cores outputs then it will choose one of the agreed CORDIC cores outputs and connect these outputs to the global outputs. Figure 4 shows the voting algorithm architecture. In our case First CORDIC and the third CORDIC will have matched outputs, and second CORDIC will have zero outputs. The controller will connect one of the first or third CORDIC core outputs to the global outputs and ignore the second CORDIC core outputs as its outputs is defected from the Trojan thread.

The simulation results are represented in figure 5. In the simulation we can see that the global outputs [X_o, Y_o] is not affected by the zeros come from CORDIC₂.

Fig. 4. Voting algorithm architecture.

/b/theta_i	25735	25164	25735	26307	26879
/b/theta_j	45	44	45	46	47
/b/x_o	23168	23570	23168	22758	22342
/b/y_o	23167	22758	23167	23570	23964
/b/UUT/cordic_1/x_o	23168	23570	23168	22758	22342
/b/UUT/cordic_1/y_o	23167	22758	23167	23570	23964
/b/UUT/cordic_2/x_o	0	23570	23168	0	
/b/UUT/cordic_2/y_o	0	22758	23167	0	
/b/UUT/cordic_3/x_o	23168	23570	23168	22758	22342
/b/UUT/cordic_3/y_o	23167	22758	23167	23570	23964

Fig. 5. Voting algorithm outputs with defected CORDIC.

B. Lockup Table Technique

In this technique we will use lockup table which contains some of the expected outputs from CORDIC [X_o, Y_o]. These outputs are limited to predefined input angles, so the lockup table contains few samples of the outputs due to the size limitations. As shown in figure 6 the controller will compare the outputs from First CORDIC core and the Second CORDIC core according to the values in the lockup table. This comparison will happen if the input angle exists in the lockup table. If the outputs are matched then it will connect one of the CORDIC cores outputs to the global outputs. If there is difference between the expected values in the lockup table and

the outputs values from any of the CORDIC cores then it will ignore all the outputs from the infected core and connect the global outputs to the core which its outputs match the lockup table values.

The simulation results are represented in figure 7. In the simulation we can see that the global outputs [X_o, Y_o] is affected by the zeros come from CORDIC₁ core for a while. Then when there is input angle exist in the lockup table, the lockup table outputs did not match the CORDIC₁ core outputs, and match CORDIC₂ core outputs. The controller will change mux_sel to choose CORDIC₂ core outputs to be connected to the global outputs.

Trojan thread attack. It compares the outputs from two CORDIC cores to the outputs of the lockup table. If one of the CORDIC cores is infected the controller will detect it and move selection to the other CORDIC core which its outputs match lockup table outputs.

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